

THE IMPORTANCE OF MODERN APPROACHES AND CREATIVE THINKING IN THE TEACHING OF HISTORY

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Abstract: The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted the national program for the development of public education for 2022-2026. Forming the knowledge and skills of school teachers, educating them in the spirit of loyalty to national and universal values, increasing the prestige of the teaching profession and the quality of pedagogues, improving textbooks and teaching methods based on the requirements of the times, bringing public education institutions to international standards. In order to build responsive modern models, many tasks were set before public education workers.

Key words: Education, school, third renaissance, didactics, interactive, creativity, electronic textbook, didactic.

In particular, the teacher assigns great responsibility to pedagogues in the implementation of these tasks. In this regard, there have been significant changes in the improvement of qualifications and retraining of public education workers. Teachers can increase their qualifications in any way they want, online or offline, not every five years, but every year. This article will discuss them. Key words: Educational system, didactics, interactive methods, modern model, international standards, "VR 360", "ISPRING" and "HotPotatos" programs. In order to improve my skills, I took lessons from teachers through special courses. In the course of my education, I got additional information about the requirements for today's classes. The most basic requirements for the current modern lesson: I - Didactic requirements II - Psychological requirements III - Hygienic requirements IV - Technological requirements Based on these requirements, attention should be paid to the following: 1. Clear and positive fulfillment of the DTS requirement. 2. Determining the possibility of the student's level of knowledge, taking into account the age of the students. 3. Directing students to a specific goal based on their interest. 4. Forming the level of knowledge of students based on the program, paying attention to independent thinking, correct and objective assessment of creative works. To

properly encourage his behavior and diligence to knowledge based on creative scores, pay attention to free thinking to improve his memory. 5. Organization of the scientific environment through the rational planning of the lesson. 6. Conveying to children the concepts, definitions, theorems, events that students should learn in the lesson based on the requirements of the time. Forming a worldview through these, giving importance to interdisciplinary connections. 7. Forming the skills and qualifications of students, directing them to the profession based on the student's ability and the demand of the time. 8. The use of visual aids that give thought, practice, innovate, teach positive work in the lesson, organize problem lessons. Improving students' thinking, teaching them to analyze information and data. 9. By introducing differential education, objectively evaluate the level of students' knowledge in the rating system. 10. Teaching students analysis, synthesis and efficient use of time. 11. Equipping the classroom based on modern requirements, paying attention to the effective use of scientific and technical progress and the availability of auxiliary tools.

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